

The Influence of Digitalization on the Evangelism Ministry of the Church: A Case Study of Dunamis International Gospel Centre, Agbor

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Abstract

Evangelism through digitalization has become prevalent in recent times. The digital world is undoubtedly influencing the context of Church services and activities. The application of digital technology to propagate the gospel, spread religious tenets and fellowship online, has resulted in reaching the unsaved in far distant areas. The research seeks to explore and bring to bear the influence of digitalization on the evangelism ministry of Dunamis International Gospel Centre. The paper adopted investigative, historical-descriptive approach. An Oral interview conducted among members of Dunamis Gospel Center, Agbor revealed that the Church headquarter located in Abuja, Nigeria has long introduced the utilization of digital and electronic communication which has been effectively practiced and extended to the Satellite Centers for over twelve years. The congregations often communicate information within and outside the Church through the use of social media such as Facebooks, Blogs, YouTube, internet, Whatsapp, Twitter, Instagram and others. It was discovered that they could easily reach out to people, including friends by sharing links and online messages in different format as part of evangelism. They only need internet connection to be part of the service. The Church official website serves as a tool for evangelistic purpose, supplying materials for individuals in need of spiritual guidance. Digital evangelism has also yielded tremendous increase in salvation of souls and membership of Dunamis Church across the globe. Based on the numerous benefits associated with digitalization, the study recommended that the universal Church must of necessity adopt and utilize the digital technology to effectively transmit the Good News, while staying focused in the teaching of the Bible. This will enhance the fulfillment of the divine mandate in a digitally connected society.

Keywords: Digitalization, Evangelism, Church, Dunamis, Agbor

Introduction

In recent years, the rapid upsurge in the utilization of information communication technology (ICT) in various spheres of human endeavours proposes appropriate approach to evangelism of the Church. The Church has the mandate to spread the gospel to the nooks and crannies of the universe. The Bible tags this "The Great Commission" to be executed faithfully by the followers of Jesus Christ (Matt. 28: 19-20). As a missionary religion, Christianity is saddled with the responsibility of disseminating information which is the essence of digital technology. Through digitalization, the Church is bound to register huge success in her evangelistic ministry. Thus, in this digital era, the method of evangelism should change from physical presence or meeting in-person to online evangelism.

The power of digital media has therefore made the Church to be able to spread its message efficiently and involve persons globally, contributing to the expansion of the Church. Digitalization has played a critical role in fostering discipleship and spiritual development within the Church, hence religious institutions have had to get used to the changing setting of innovation. Dunamis International Gospel Centre, Agbor serves as a case study to critically investigate the influence of digitalization on the evangelism ministry of the Church. Against this

backdrop, this study explores how the above named Church integrates digital application in the process of its spirituality, evangelism and overall religious experiences. To achieve this objective, the paper adopts investigative, historical-descriptive approach.

Conceptual Clarifications

Digitalization: This is the process of transforming various categories of information such as texts, sound, visuals, video and data obtained from a variety of sources into digital language. Digitalization is also referred to as the method of using digital technologies and data in order to provide information within and outside the Church. It is a term that depicts digital innovations with respect to the use of digital technologies to spread information to the entire society. Furthermore, it refers to diverse methods of restructuring several areas of social life through digital communication and media equipment. Digitalization therefore involves the use of social media such as Facebooks, Blogs, YouTube, internet, Whatsapp, Myspace, Twitter (now X), Instagram the internet, email, videos, websites, phones to disseminate information. It enhances the opportunity to convert ideas, graphics, software code and other digital applications into unique forms that is beyond human comprehension. Digitalization could be used interchangeably with digital media, digital technology, digital application, digital communication among others.

Evangelism: Evangelism originated from the Greek word, *Euangelion*, which is interpreted as Good News of the Gospel. The term could also be defined as the method of propagating the gospel to the world. Moreover, it is the art of preaching the Good News of Jesus for the purpose of winning souls to the Christian faith. Thus, Christianity is the only religious sect that regards it as *soul hunt* evangelism. There are two types of evangelism, namely Public and Personal evangelism accompanied by a variety of methods and approaches such as Open- Air Preaching, Trickle-Down Evangelism, Door to Door Evangelism, Soul Winning through Salvation Messages, Evangelism through Practical Christian Living, Creative Evangelism through the use of music and drama, Distribution of Gospel Tracts, Crusades and others.

Apparently, proclaiming the gospel by means of the above methods is one of the ways Christians can fulfill Christ's call to be his witnesses (Acts 1:8). Evangelism brings all nations together by reconciling all mankind to God through Jesus Christ. Inadvertently, digital evangelism is currently a swift avenue for advancing the message of Jesus Christ to the universe. It entails using digital media which includes social media, the internet, email, videos, websites, phones and others to reach out to the needy, as well as the unsaved people in far distant areas for the purpose of sharing the Gospel online and converting souls to Christ.

Church: The Greek name for Church is *ekklesia*, meaning *those called out*. It is both an organism and organization. It is an organism in the sense that it is united around the saving work of Christ. It is an organization in that it gathers around a common purpose and doctrine. The Church denotes the "assembly" or congregation of people who believe in Jesus Christ and uphold his principles. Implicitly, it refers to the Christian community redeemed by God. The Church is not necessarily a building, but the body of Christ with a peculiar nature and intention. These biblical responsibilities of the Church are fundamental to Christians. The Church portends both visible and invisible, hence it is both local and universal.

History of Dunamis International Gospel Center

Dunamis International Gospel Centre was founded by Pastor Dr. Paul Enenche on the 10th of November, 1996. The Church held her first Sunday service at the Abuja Centre for Arts and Culture. They spent two weeks at that location before relocating to the Abuja Sheraton Hotel and Towers, where worship lasted for six months. Interestingly, this Church which had a humble beginning has produced several branches within and outside Nigeria. It is an inter-denominational Mega- Church with over 100,000 members worldwide and in Nigeria. The current leaders of the Church are Senior Pastors Paul and Becky- Paul Enenche. They work in synergy with several other pastors. The Church holds Healing and Deliverance Services every Tuesday at 9:30am. Others are the Power Communion Service and Worship, Word and Wonders Night, being held every Wednesday at 5: 00pm

and last Friday of every month at 9:30pm respectively. The essence of these programs is to motivate members to be seriously involved in worship despite their physical location. The use of digital media by the Church has made online worship an essential part of its members' spiritual voyage. The International headquarter of Dunamis Church (The Glory Dome) Lord's Garden, Airport Road Abuja, Nigeria, was dedicated on 24th November, 2018. The founder who happens to be a medical doctor is happily married to Dr. (Mrs.) Becky Enenche and they are blessed with children. The church has its international branches in Spain, United Kingdom among others.

Dunamis Vision, Mission, Goal and Beliefs

Vision: *The Restoration of human destiny and dignity by the administration of the benefits of Redemption, through the ministry of the blood and the demonstration of power.*

Mission: *To blanket this world with the evidence of God's saving, healing, delivering and lifting power every people live, work or play, until the earth is filled with the knowledge of the glory of the Lord as the waters cover the seas (November 14:21, Isaiah 11:9 and Habakkuk 2:14).*

Dunamis Church Goal: *Connecting humanity with the person, Presence, (for), Purpose, Potential, Principles and Power of the Almighty and releasing them to subdue and dominate the earth now and possess Heaven at the end.*

Dunamis Church Beliefs: *Many have heard the Gospel but need to see God in action. Therefore, we celebrate the power and presence of God demonstrated in the lives of His children, through the very many signs and wonders that characterize our meetings (Mark 16:20).*

Dunamis International Gospel Center, Agbor

Dunamis International Gospel Center, Agbor was established on the 8th of March, 2015. It started from Shalom Christian Center, Boji-Boji, Owa with Pastor Samuel Opalua as the pioneer pastor. The first service was held on the same day with about thirty-eight members. Those in attendance included Professor and Professor (Mrs) P. N. Okoh; Dr. and Dr. (Mrs) Onwuegbu; Mr. and Mrs Onyela; Mrs Eboh; Lilian; Shedrach and others. The Church is currently located at the premises of Word of Faith Group of Schools, Kikanwa Street, Boji-Boji, Owa. Dunamis Center, Agbor is fully engaged in digital service and evangelism which has attracted several members to the Church. All the services at the national headquarter are transmitted through digital media to satellite branches which includes the Agbor Center.

Digital Integration in Dunamis Gospel Church

In response to digital revolution which has pervaded the society, institutions and religious organizations are currently changing their mode of operation to improve public service delivery. Inadvertently, the development of digital technology has created a shift from individual to communal means of connectivity and interactions through digital application. Such system of communication involves the use of computers and social media among the world community. Implicitly, the awareness of the crucial nature of digitalization propelled the Dunamis Church to consciously integrate the system into their Church service and evangelism ministry. The essence of this new invention is to enhance their mode of conveying the Christian Faith within and outside the Church. Essentially, the propagation of the gospel is the duty of the Church which every member must participate irrespective of the distance.

A member of Dunamis Church, Agbor, observed that as a Commission entrusted with the mandate to convert souls to the kingdom of God through the Gospel, the Church transmits their beliefs and practices; experiences; testimonies and other vital information through the application of social media such as Blogs, Facebook, Whatsapp, Myspace, Twitter (now X), YouTube, Instagram as well as Television and Radio Stations

to accomplish the purpose. He further reiterates that communication of the Good News is the utmost focus of Dunamis Church which necessitated their adoption of several evangelistic patterns in their outreach. Apparently, digitalization has become a household method of preaching the gospel, particularly in Dunamis Centre. According to another interviewee, Dunamis International Gospel Centre is cognizant of the benefits of attracting wider audience through the use of digital technology. Consequently, live stream platforms are utilized to broadcast their worship services, evangelism and other events. Prior to COVID-19 pandemic, the Church was used to transmitting their Sunday and Midweek services through digital media. Incidentally, while most Churches were faced with the challenge of switching from analogue to digital preaching, Dunamis had a smooth ride and became a channel of blessing to myriad families, both Christians and none Christians within and outside Nigeria. The Church auditorium has a sitting capacity of thirty thousand (30, 000) members, hence five services are conducted every Sunday and two services every Wednesday which is the mid-week service. All these worship services and other programs are featured online.

As a matter of fact, the Church began to engage in digital media for over a decade. There are platforms fashioned for children, teenagers, youths and adults for networking, prayer and digital evangelism. Interestingly, the satellite Churches including Agbor branch easily connect to every program at the national headquarters, Abuja. Moreso, Dunamis Centre has a regular website with various sections and links which aid the dissemination of the gospel. The Church owns a personal Satellite television and radio stations in Nigeria which feature a series called “Destiny Encounter” These are often streamed online with millions of viewers’ worldwide. Thus, having been in existence for quite some time, Dunamis television celebrated her twelfth (12th) year anniversary on the 15th of September, 2023. Moreover, it was posited that other digital evangelistic channels of the commission are the Seed of Destiny Devotional; Media and Resource; and Dunamis Christian Academy. Inadvertently, digital evangelism extends beyond social media postings. Rather, it entails attending to the needs of the less privileged and challenges of other people by means of content and interaction, establishing cordial relationships, and most importantly, pointing individuals to Christ. Indeed, this all embracing assignment involves both pastors and the congregation, hence the Dunamis family work in synergy to realize this goal.

The Effects of Digital Evangelism of Dunamis International Gospel Centre

Digital evangelism is an important tool for the members of the above named Church because it enables them to be involved with other people on a deeper level by sharing crucial information about their belief which may be of help to those who need such assistance. This method of evangelism-digital technology provides avenues of reaching more people than ever before with the gospel.

Bringing the Gospel to the World: Digital application is one of the most effective means that Dunamis Church reach out to people across the globe. It does not make the Church to discriminate against anybody, either on language or ethnic background. Rather, it provides access for it to relate with the persons in their home, countries, at work or anywhere else. Obviously, digital evangelism enables the Church to minister to the whole world at the same time. it is very easy to reach out to people, including friends by sharing links and online messages in different format as part of evangelism. They only need internet connection to be part of the service. The Church official website serves as a tool for evangelistic purpose, supplying materials for individuals in need of spiritual guidance. Through digital application; Dunamis Church has extended its evangelistic tentacles, reaching people who may not have been exposed to it through physical location.

Accepting Online Worship: Dunamis International Gospel Centre has embraced the capacity of digital application to expand its reach and engage with a wider audience. Through the method of life streaming platforms, the Church broadcasts its services and events online. One notable instance is the Healing and Deliverance Service which holds every Tuesday at 9:30am. Others are the Power Communion Service and Worship, Word and Wonders Night, being held every Wednesday at 5: 00pm and last Friday of every month at 9:30pm respectively. These ideas have made the Church to be brought near to its members and enabled them to be seriously involved in worship in spite of their physical location. The use of digital application by the Church has made online worship

an important aspect of its members' spiritual journey. Interestingly, it has boosted people's chances of listening to God's word.

Promoting Followership and Spiritual Growth: Digital evangelism has performed a significant role in fostering followership and spiritual growth within Dunamis Church. The ministry has evolved mobile applications and online platforms that create room to devotionals known as seeds of Destiny, Bible Study materials, messages and resources. These methods provide forum for members to involve with spiritual content comfortably, strengthened their understanding of the Bible and confirming their belief. Aniebiet remarks that online services have helped him to equip his library digitally because archiving of messages is made easy. He also states that online services have simplified Bible Study and made possible repeated studies at his convenient time, especially through supported playback device.

Church Expansion: Digital technology has been of immense importance in the expansion of the Church. The reason being that most of the branches of the Church today started as satellite Churches. It is very easy to start a satellite Church because anyone who has benefitted from the online streaming of the Church over time will definitely like to identify with the branch of the Church closer to them because it is cost. Through the online programmes, people locate the nearest branch to them and attend. Distance is no longer a barrier from listening to the word of God. It also provides forum for people to be delivered and healed.

Easy Access to Members: Churches like Dunamis Center that are on digital technology can interact with and easily have access to their members than those that stick to traditional forms of physical contact. Digital technology is an incredibly strong way for Dunamis to reach many people. With over four billion serious users, social medial platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Instagrams and Whatsapp can aid the Church connect people who may never have heard of it. By sharing messages and inspiring people through digital technology, you are providing access for people to locate the Church. With live streaming programmes online, there is the opportunity for members in any part of the world to view.

Building Relationships with Younger Generations: These generations are seriously turning to social media platforms for information and interactions. With technology, Dunamis Church is able to build a virile relationship with younger generations and attract new members who may not have initially thought of going to the Church. These younger generations are the most active on social media platforms. It becomes necessary to easily reach them where they are already spending their time. It helps to connect these young ones on a more personal level, enabling you to share your experiences, testimonies and challenges in a manner that can promote empathy, understanding and relationship. It can also be a strong method for Dunamis Church to establish relationships with the younger generations by providing a more reachable, involving, authentic, and connected presence online.

Expansion of Outreaches: Even though digitalization cannot replace traditional method of reaching people, it certainly can extend the efforts of outreaches. In the process of sharing soul lifting messages, exhorting members to share their faith and supplying resources for persons who may be facing challenges, the Church can expand its reach for beyond the physical contacts. When one post is formed, it can live on for a long period of time and by implication, reach more people.

Conclusion

Dunamis International Gospel Centre serves as a case study of how digital evangelism has impacted religious institutions. By accepting digital application, the Church has extended its reach, magnified its evangelistic efforts, fostered fellowship, and spiritual growth. The Healing and Deliverance service, worship, word and wonders' Night and the two Sunday Services are testaments to the positive influence of digital evangelism on the Church. She continues to excel and get used to the developing needs of her members in this overwhelming digital era. Dunamis Church stands as a beacon of how digital evangelism can be harnessed to spread the good news and develop spiritual growth in the 21st century.

Recommendations

The Church must of necessity adopt and utilize the digital technology to effectively transmit the Good News. The Church should accept changes while staying focused in the teaching of the Bible. Digital technology should become part and parcel in the journey of the Church in reaching to people with the gospel of salvation. This will enhance the fulfillment of the divine mandate in a digitally connected society.

Endnotes

1. G. K. Pakpahan, et al., "Social Media and Evangelism for Millennial Generation." *Advances in Social Science Education and Humanities Research*. (2021), 699.
2. J. Reis, et al, *Digitalization: A Literature Review and Research Agenda*. (Online) (2020), 1-14.
3. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340067801> Retrieved 18th October, 2023.
4. C. Perez, "From Long Waves to Great Surges," *European Journal of Economics and Social Sciences*. 27, 1-2 (2015), 69-80.
5. J. Srari & H. Lorentz, "Developing Design Principles for the Digitalization of Purchasing and Supply Management," *Journal of Purchase and Supply Management*. 25(1) (2019), 78-98.
6. United Bible Society Dictionary. BibleWorks. [C:\Users\Victory\Documents\BibleWorks7\init\bw700.swc (2007).
7. P. O. Amanze & C. N. Wogu, *Internet Evangelism: An Effective Method for Soul Winning in the Seventh-Day Adventist Church in Nigeria* (2015), 4-5. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/306048920>. Retrieved on 18th October, 2023.
8. B. G. Nsensereka, & T. Nwanze, "Evangelism in the Era of New Media," *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Sciences (IJRISS)* 5 (8) (2021), 1.
9. T Adeyemo, *African Bible Commentary* (Kenya: Zondervan Publishers, 2006), 34.
10. M. I. Okafor, *A Contextual Interpretation of Acts 6:1-6 as a Model for Conflict Management in some Pentecostal Churches in Delta North Senatorial District*. A Thesis Submitted to the Post Graduate School (unpublished) DELSU, Abraka. (2020), 89.
11. R. Velarde, *What is the Church?* (2009):1-2. <https://www.focusonthefamily.com> Retrieved 18th October, 2023
12. S. Opaluwa, Interviewed, October 21, 2023
13. M. Iwekogwu, Interviewed, October 22, 2023
14. P. Enenche, *About Dunamis International Gospel Centre* (2023):1-3. From <https://dunamispentecost.org>. Retrieved on October 25, 2023.
15. Samuel Opaluwa, Interviewed, October 22, 2023.
16. S. Aniebiet Interviewed, October 21, 2023.
17. T. Ozukum, *The Impact of Social Media on Religious Tolerance in India. A Case Study on Digital Discourse in Religious Conflicts* (2021):7-12. <https://www.researchgate.net> 3544 Retrieved 18th October, 2023
18. G. K. Pakpahan, et al. *Social Media and Evangelism for Millennial Generation*, *Advances in Social Science Education and Humanities Research*. (2021), 699.
19. S. Aniebiet, Interviewed, October 21, 2023.
20. A. Olorunfemi, Interviewed, October 22, 2023.
21. E. S. Okolie, Interviewed, October 22, 2023.
22. C. Nwaka, Interviewed, October 22, 2023
23. J. C. Ugwuagbo, Interviewed, October 22, 2023
24. Samuel Opaluwa, Interviewed, October 22, 2023
25. M. Iwekogwu, Interviewed, October 22, 2023
26. S. Aniebiet, Interviewed, October 21, 2023
27. I. Uwuike, Interviewed, October 22, 2023
28. D. Davis, *Don't Ignore These Five Benefits of Social Media for Your Church* (2023): 1-5. From <https://www.churchfluence.com> Retrieved on October, 30, 23.
29. Ibid, 7-8